

The Sanctuary of the Egyptian Gods at Gortyn

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Entry tags: Greece, Aegean, Graeco-Roman, Egyptian Religions, Temple, Religious Place, Religious Group, Crete

It was 1914 when G. Oliverio unearthed the first parts of the temple dedicated to the Egyptian deities. The entrance of the temple is west while at the south side there is a space with more constructions being part of the same complex. On the architrave above the entrance, an inscription reveals the name of the woman who, along with her two children, are the founders of this temple. The temple is small, with very simple architecture. On the inside of the cella, there is a podium accessible through its south side by three small steps. Four marble statues were found close to the podium, three of them had evidentially fallen off there. They are identified as the statues of Isis, Serapis, and Hermanubis while the fourth statue might be one of the donors. There is also a small staircase descending to an underground construction. The area was reused in the following centuries under different contexts as the excavator mentions the presence of tombs in the northern part of the temple one of which held an important number of byzantine coins.

Date Range: 100 CE - 300 CE

Region: Gortyn

Region tags: Europe, Southeastern Europe, Greece, Crete

Gortyn is an ancient city that continued to rise under Roman rule and became the capital of the joint province of Creta et Cyrenaica. The excavations in the Roman city have revealed important public buildings, as the Praetorium, and religious sites, as the sanctuary of the Egyptian deities.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Oliverio, G. 1914. "Scoperta del Santuario delle divinità Egizie in Gortyna." *Annuario della Scuola Archeologica di Atene e delle Missioni Italiane in Oriente* 1: 376–377.
- Source 2: Salditt-Trappmann, R. 1970. *Tempel der ägyptischen Götter in Griechenland und an der Westküste Kleinasiens*. Leiden: Brill.
- Source 3: Castiglione, L. 1971. "Fragment einer thronenden Sarapis-Statue in dem Sarapieion von Gortyn." *Acta Archaeologica Academiae Scientiarum Hungaricae* 154: 229–230.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: http://odysseus.culture.gr/h/2/gh251.jsp?obj_id=14903

– Source 1 Description: Official site of the Ministry of Culture

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

↳ Type of excavation:

– Scientific

↳ Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1914

↳ Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Excavation by the Scuola Archeologica di Atene e delle Missioni Italiane in Oriente

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Other [specify]: No

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

↳ Type of feature

– Water feature

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

↳ Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– No

Notes: It was close to other important structures of Roman Gortyn but the excavations have

not revealed in detail the urban plan.

Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

A single structure

– No

Notes: It is a sanctuary that comprises more than one structure. The temple, with a very simple plan. A parallel wall to the south wall of the temple, divided into two parts: the first one creates the south part of a basin, and the second one limits the north part of a rectangular room in which there is a small staircase descending to a square underground chamber. Parallel to the crypt and towards the south, there is another small construction. The excavations in the area in front of the temple unearthed also a stylobates that supported six columns with Ionic capitals.

One single feature

– Other [specify]: No

A group of structures:

– Yes

Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– Yes

A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

Notes: It was in use for more than two centuries.

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

Notes: There is a previous phase in the sanctuary which had never been completely covered. Between the temple and the underground chamber, two walls exist. It could be considered that they were not built at the same time and that the underground chamber pre-existed the temple. A close study of the architecture suggests that the temple and the crypt do not belong to the same time period. In addition, the area was reused in the following centuries under different contexts as the excavator mentions the presence of tombs in the northern part of the temple.

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

– Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

– Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

– Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– No

Notes: The inscription that commemorates the construction of the temple dates to the end of the first or the beginning of the 2nd century CE. It was found in front of the facade of the temple where a limestone architrave of a length of 2,35 m stood carrying the inscription. It commemorates that Flavia Filira with her children, Gaius Metronius Maximus, Filira, and Lyskia dedicated the temple to the gods. Filira is an unicum in Crete and it is suggested that comes from a phytonym which would be translated as tilia. Using such a name was common for manumissions.

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

↳ Groups:

– Other [specify]: The information known concerns only the temple, which was constructed by a woman and her children.

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Field doesn't know

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

↳ Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– Yes

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Thanksgiving to a god/gods for favor received

Notes: The inscription says "Εἷσιδι καὶ Σαράπιδι καὶ θεοῖς συννάοις Φλαβία Φιλύρα μετὰ τῶν| τέκνων Γ(αίου) Μετρωνίου Μαξι[μου] καὶ Φιλύρας καὶ Λυσκίας τὸν οἶκον ἐκ θεμελίων |κατασκευάσσαα κα[θίδρυ]σεν εὐχὴν καὶ χαριστήιον".

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

Notes: There is a temple and a structure south of the temple that is divided into two parts. One of these parts is the structure that in the bibliography is known as "the crypt". Parallel to the crypt and towards the south, there is also another small construction. In front of the temple, there was a stylobates which supported six columns with Ionic capitals.

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– No

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Notes: The main temple seems to be the center of the cult but there were other auxiliary spaces.

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:
Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.
– Field doesn't know

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:
– Field doesn't know

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth
– No

↳ Sand
– No

↳ Clay
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Plaster

– Field doesn't know

↳ Wood

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Grass

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: Bricks

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

Notes: The sanctuary offered to the research an important number of statues preserved in very good condition - three statues were found in the cellar. The excavation was also rich in small artefacts such as the lower part of a female statuette, two female torsos, three fragmentary terracotta heads of women, small terracotta bulls and other small ex-votos.

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

Notes: There is an inscription on the architrave when entering the temple.

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

Notes: There were statues and probably other artifacts that have not survived.

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

Notes: In the cella of the temple, four statues were excavated. Three of them belonged to the podium of the cella, dating around 180-190 CE: Isis, Serapis, and a young man. West of the western wall of the crypt another statue was brought to light: a headless marble male statue sited on a throne.

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Isis, Serapis, Anubis.

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– No

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

Notes: A female statue, larger than human size, was found in the cella. It has been suggested that this statue is a representation of Flavia Filyra, the donor of the temple.

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– Yes

Notes: The third statue found on the podium of the cella is a statue of a young man that holds over the left shoulder a caduceus. In addition, a head of a dog was found close to the statue. Therefore it has been identified as the jackal-headed Hermanubis.

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Field doesn't know

↳ Floral motifs

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

Notes: The inscription that commemorates the construction of the temple was found carved on the facade of the temple where a limestone architrave of a length of 2,35 m stood.

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there statues present:

– Yes

↳ Cult statues:

– Yes

Notes: It is possible that the statues found in the cella of the temple were cult statues.

↳ Statues of gods/supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: A statue of Isis, two statues of Serapis, a statue of Anubis/Hermanubis.

↳ Statues of humans:

– Yes

Notes: A female statue, probably the donor.

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Probably yes but nothing survives.

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

Notes: In total, 7 inscriptions were found in the Isiac sanctuary of Gortyn.

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative

[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

Notes: The inscriptions give information on the donors, the deities worshiped in the

temple, and the relation that was created between the deities and the devotees.

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– Yes

Notes: At least two of the total seven inscriptions are dedications accompanied by the expression *χαριστήιον*.

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

↳ Other type of decoration:

– Field doesn't know

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: Anubis as a jackal-headed dog.

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– No

↳ Humans

– Yes

↳ Supernatural narratives

– No

↳ Human narratives

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– No

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– Yes

|

↳ Is the cult statue visible:
– Yes

↳ Is the cult statue hidden:
– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural monitoring of norm adherence:
– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect offerings:
– Yes

↳ Libations:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Offerings of food:
– Yes [specify]: Field doesn't know

↳ Animal sacrifice:
– Yes [specify]: Field doesn't know

↳ Human sacrifice:
– No

↳ Sacred objects:
– Yes [specify]: Field doesn't know

↳ Daily life objects:
– Yes [specify]: Field doesn't know

↳ Other:

–Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect maintenance of the place:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect personal hygiene:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honoring oaths:

– Yes

↳ Other:

–Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

Notes: They communicate through dedications, dreams, oracles etc.

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– No

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

Are there animal sacrifices:

– Yes [specify]: We do not know the types of animals

Are there human sacrifices:

– No

Are the sacrificed humans associated in some way:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

Notes: The excavations have not revealed much, but even the statues and inscriptions found are part of the materials offered to the gods.

Are material offerings mandatory:

– No

Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Field doesn't know

Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Field doesn't know

Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– No

Other

– Other [specify]: No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Field doesn't know

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

Is it required:

– Field doesn't know

Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Field doesn't know

Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

Notes: The Roman phase of the sanctuary that survives is not the first phase of construction. Probably, a sanctuary was built there since the Hellenistic times.

Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Field doesn't know

Other

–Other [specify]: No

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Field doesn't know

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Field doesn't know

Are festivals present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: No evidence comes from this sanctuary but, if related to the other cult places of the Isiac deities in the Roman world, we should expect some festivals such as the Navigium Isidis, the Sacrum Phariae, and the Inventio Osiridis.

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– Field doesn't know

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: Probably festivities open to all the members of the community or only for the initiates would take place.

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

–specify: Field doesn't know

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

–specify: Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– No

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

Notes: This sanctuary does not give enough information. Nonetheless, priests and other offices working in daily activities in the sanctuary are known from analogous sites in other parts of the Roman world, such as Athens.

↳ Present full time

– Field doesn't know

↳ Present part time

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: In some cases, such as in Beroea and Stobi, the priests held a lifelong office. It is not the norm, though, and we do not know if this was followed in this sanctuary as well.

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Field doesn't know

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Probably yes.

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– No

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Adalberto Magnelli. Il santuario delle divinità egizie a Gortyna. L'evidenza epigrafica..

Reference: Gaspare Oliverio. Scoperta del Santuario delle divinità Egizie in Gortyna.